

Barnga

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Keywords

Conflict Management, Culture, Diversity, Inclusion, Intercultural Communication, Sociology, Team Development

Figure 1. Cover of *Barnga* (25th Anniversary Edition) by Sivasailam Thiagarajan. Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Barnga is an intercultural simulation game developed by Sivasailam Thiagarajan in 1980 (see Figure 1). The first official Barnga game manual was created in the 1990s by Barbara Steinwachs and is now available in its 25th edition (Thiagarajan, 2006). The aim of the game is to raise participants' awareness of cultural differences and misunderstandings in communication. The game conveys the experience of a "culture shock" by showing how different understandings of rules can lead to confusion and conflict. It is aimed at people who work or study in intercultural teams, and is also well suited to sensitizing inexperienced individuals, such as young students, to this important topic. Barnga's game concept is offered in various levels of complexity by different institutions. These range from simple PDF

instructions to fully developed games with game materials. In addition, there are also online versions of the game, such as the one by Ohmura et al. (2008).

Facts

Release date:	1980
Developer:	Sivasailam Thiagarajan
Game type:	Analog card game, intercultural simulation game
Number of players:	at least 12 players, the more, the better.
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	One round, including debriefing, takes between 40 and 70 minutes
Languages:	The game is available in several languages, depending on the materials used.
Environment:	-
Material:	1 deck of cards for each of at least three groups, different rule sets for each group, a flyer with identical game guidelines for each group
Price:	freely available, though some versions cost a small amount of money

Resonance & Criticism

The game's methods are widely regarded as simple yet effective; however, it has not won any official awards. Critics emphasize that the effectiveness of the game strongly depends on the debriefing and reflection phase, which experienced facilitators should lead.

Game Principle & Process

Participants are divided into three groups; ideally, each group has four to six players. In the original version, the card game "Five Tricks" is played within each group, but other card games can also be used as long as their rules allow variations. Each group receives a deck of cards, identical game guidelines about the general gameplay, and a specific set of slightly differing rules. After a short introductory phase, during which the guidelines are explained and players familiarize themselves with their specific rules, the players may no longer speak, and the facilitator collects all the rule sets. The only permitted form of communication is gestures. Different rules then apply at each table, without this being visible from the outside. Once a round of the card game is completed, players rotate between the groups without knowing the others' rules.

The rotation is determined at the beginning. It is advisable for winners and/or (depending on group size) losers to switch groups. The encounter with different rules often leads to confusion, frustration, and conflict, as participants realize that their familiar strategies no longer work, but the exact reason is not immediately apparent. Since the game provides little direct feedback, Barnga's effectiveness largely depends on a well-executed debriefing, reflection, and transfer phase. Here, observations are summarized, interpreted, and re-

evaluated. It is advisable to begin by letting individuals describe their experiences, thereby starting a discussion guided by the instructor.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Barnga aims to sensitize participants to the dynamics of cultural differences and their impact on communication. It promotes understanding of different behavioral strategies and reflection on unconsciously assumed rule systems. The game is particularly suitable for intercultural training and seminars to increase sensitivity and competence when dealing with cultural diversity.

As previously mentioned, there are different versions of Barnga. A clear, simple version is provided in the University of Michigan's PDF instructions.

Effectiveness

No purely empirical studies on Barnga exist. However, Fowler & Blohm (2004) highlight in their Handbook of Intercultural Training that participants often experience an “aha moment” that stimulates reflection on cultural assumptions. The extent to which the game’s difficulty aligns with players’ abilities depends entirely on how they handle the unfamiliar situation and the discrepancy between the familiar and the unfamiliar—and the misunderstandings that arise from it. Achieving a flow state may be limited by the game's deliberate creation of frustration through rule deviations. This does not typically lead to gameplay enjoyment, but the resulting cognitive dissonance (Festinger, 1957) supports involvement and thus promotes the learning goal.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Barnga deliberately induces confusion and frustration, which can be emotionally challenging for some participants, particularly those with low tolerance for ambiguity or prior negative experiences in group conflict. Without careful facilitation and a structured debriefing, participants may focus on irritation rather than reflection, potentially reinforcing stereotypes or interpersonal tension instead of promoting intercultural understanding.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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